

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF DYNAMIC YARN PULL-OUT PROCESS

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Abstract

There are different types of yarn movements that occur prior to or during fabric failure under dynamic loads. Yarn pull-out test method is an experimental approach that evaluates properties associated with yarn movement in a fabric. Yarn pull-out behavior of Kevlar KM-2 fabric with varying pull-out speeds and friction coefficients is studied by using a numerical dynamic yarn pull-out test based upon an explicit digital element method (DEM). This yarn pull-out can serve as an important energy absorption mechanism during ballistic impact of woven fabric. The study shows that pull-out force, pull-out energy, stress in pulled yarn all increase with increasing pull-out speed and friction coefficient. The maximum pull-out force and uncrimping energy increase quadratically with friction coefficient but vary linearly with pull-out speed. The pull-out zone propagates fast along pulled yarn to disturb the yarn structure, while yarn uncrimping spreads and yarn sliding transfers gradually to the free end.

Introduction

Yarn stretch, uncrimping, and slip are different types of yarn movements that occur prior to or during fabric failure under dynamic loads. As such, an experimental or numerical method is needed to investigate interactions between yarns and evaluate yarn resistance against movement, especially for large deformation such as tearing and ballistic impact. The yarn pull-out test method is an experimental approach that evaluates these properties and is a bridge to fabric ballistic resistance investigations. In yarn pull-out test, a selected yarn in the middle of a fabric is simply pulled out of the weave, and the pull-out force along with yarn displacement is recorded for the purpose of mechanical and inter-yarn property evaluation. Many variations to the yarn pull-out apparatus have been developed. The earlier pull-out test approach was developed by Sebastian et al. [1, 2] and

Motamedi et al. [3] by mounting fabric on a frame, connecting a selected yarn to a hook, and moving the frame. They studied yarn pull-out from plain woven cotton fabrics. Martinez et al. [4] studied the friction force required to completely pull out a single yarn from Kevlar fabrics by loading a static pressure over the full area of the fabric. Both groups found that pull-out force increased as fabric length increased. Bazhenov [5] performed yarn pull-out test on Aramid fabrics with different yarn counts and denier. The experiment utilized a fabric holding fixture at the bottom that was flat on left and right sides and curved up as U-shape in the middle (referred to as PI-shape by the author). The free end of the pulled yarn was centered under the U-shape section and was therefore unconstrained, while the fabric was clamped by the flat sides. The transverse edges were also unconstrained. Although this setup eliminates the effect of fixture, it has several limitations: the fabric cannot displace at the clamped end; once the fabric was clamped, only one pull-out test can be performed; and the setup does not allow transverse force to be applied. It was found that the maximum pull-out force increased linearly with fabric length and a linear relation existed between the uncrimping portion of the curve and yarn displacement. Shockey et al. [6] improved the pull-out test design by clamping and preloading the fabric's transverse edges. A strong dependency of pull-out force to yarn count and transverse force was shown in his study. Similar methods with some minor modifications have been employed in numerous studies [7, 9-17]. The improved design simplifies tests not only by eliminating the fixture effects but also by performing a series of pull-out experiments without repositioning the grips at the edges. Kirkwood et al. [7, 8] performed an edge and center yarn pull-out experiments on Kevlar KM2 to investigate the relationship between yarn pull-out energy and ballistic energy absorption and found that yarn uncrimping and yarn translation are important mechanisms of energy absorption. King

[9] conducted a series of experimental studies on frictional resistance of Kevlar yarns at different rates to observe both qualitative and quantitative properties of the frictional forces that resist yarn slip.

Although there has been much experimental yarn pull-out research at the quasi static level, there has only been a limited number of numerical studies to investigate the pull-out behavior of yarn. Dong et al. [11] introduced a 2D simplified FEM model to investigate the pull-out behavior by varying cross yarn and parallel fiber friction, as well as fiber diameter and fabric count. They found that cross-yarn friction increases the pull-out force, but parallel fiber friction does not affect the pull-out force significantly. Valizadeh et al [13] created a meso-level FEM 3D model for the plain woven fabric using explicit ABAQUS code. Zhu et al. [14] created a 3D FEM model for Kevlar 49 fabric at the yarn-level using LS-DYNA with a high pull-out velocity up to 1 m/s in comparison to experimental tests. The pull-out force obtained from the numerical model was higher than that obtained from the experiment due to consideration of continuum solid yarns. This paper presents a numerical study of dynamic yarn pull-out behavior of Kevlar KM2 fabric in a fiber-level yarn structure. The effects of pull-out velocity and friction coefficient will be investigated. The pull-out velocity in this study uses up to 50 m/s, a velocity high enough to allow for a comparison to yarn pull-out velocity (expected $V_i > 17$ m/s [8]) under a ballistic impact.

Numerical Model

A micro-scale (fiber-level) computational method, based on the digital element method, refer to Zhou et al. [18], Miao et al. [19], and Wang et al. [20], has been developed to numerically simulate the impact of yarn pull-out. Based on this method, a relaxed 34×34 yarn fabric geometry is generated for the yarn pull-out test. Generating a relaxed, accurate geometry is essential to performing the initial stage of the yarn pull-out simulation. An assembly of 19 digital fibers per yarn was used in this modeled geometry. The convergence of modeled yarn assemblies in digital element method was checked elsewhere [20]. Fig. 1a shows the geometric model of the fabric for yarn pull-out. The transverse ends of the fabric (top and bottom ends in Fig. 1a) are preloaded up to $220 \text{ N} \pm 2\%$. The ends of the fabric in the pull-out direction (left and right ends in Fig. 1a) are unconstrained. The middle yarn is pulled out

with a constant velocity of 10, 20, 30, 40, or 50 m/s in the unconstrained direction. Three different levels of friction coefficients (0.2, 0.3, and 0.4) are used in each pull-out speed.

Fig. 1. Yarn pull-out process shown in three stages

Fig. 2. Yarn pull-out force-displacement profile (The pull-out velocity is 10 m/s)

Numerical Results and Discussion

The yarn pull-out process can be divided into two stages. In the first stage, the middle yarn is pulled

out from the right edge of the fabric with a constant velocity. The pulled yarn uncrimps, followed by cross-yarns separating from the edges of the fabric as shown in Fig 1a. In the second stage, the free end of the pulled yarn slides between unconstrained neighboring yarns and over the cross-yarns, as shown in Fig. 1b. Fig. 2 shows the pull-out force and the corresponding average free edge pull-out velocity as functions of yarn displacement. In stage 1, the pull-out force increases and reaches its maximum when the pulled yarn fully stretches. This is called yarn uncrimping, where the pulled yarn progressively straightens and locally disturbs the woven yarn structure [6]. In stage 2, the pull-out force oscillates regularly. The oscillation in the force-displacement curve corresponds to the pull-out yarn passing each cross-yarn. Both the mean value and the oscillating amplitude decrease until the yarn is completely pulled out. Stage 2 is defined as “yarn translation”. The pull-out force exhibits an irregular decrease and larger wave length at the first oscillation after the peak force. This is due to both the yarn translation and edge cross-yarn separation occurring at the same time. This edge cross-yarn separation is caused by the leading cross-yarn being dragged away from the fabric at the right edge and slipping along the unconstrained yarns that neighbor the pulled yarn. At the left edge, the trailing cross-yarns that no longer interlock with the pulled yarn try to remain straight [9] under the transverse tension, while the remaining cross-yarns are pulled toward the right under the friction from the pulled yarn. This causes the non-interlocking cross-yarns to separate from the rest of the fabric. When the free end of the pull-out yarn passes each cross-yarn, there are one maximum and one minimum in the pull-out force vs. displacement curve. The region corresponding to these minimum and maximum points is called slip-stick region [17]; the yarn passing over or under the cross-yarn, while the end is bent and stick to the cross-yarn, is described as the stick motion, whereas the yarn passing between the two cross-yarns is described as the slip motion. This behavior is shown in Fig. 3 in which the free end of pulled yarn passes three cross-yarns. The stick motion causes maxima, while slip motion causes minima in the pull-out force.

Fig. 4 shows the displacement as a function of time at two ends of the pulled yarn. Since the right end of the yarn is pulled at a constant speed, the displacement increases linearly with time, while the free end of the pull-out yarn shows an oscillation in

the curve as is shown in the pull-out force curve whose behavior is expected. This oscillation in the displacement of free end is depicted in Fig. 3 as well when it moves up and down while passing each cross-yarn. Both velocity and displacement at free end show an approximately linear increase in stage 1 before yarn slipping starts. It can be described as fabric movement in the yarn pull-out process. Fig. 5a-e shows the representative pull-out curve for different pull-out speeds and friction coefficients. Three different friction coefficients (0.2, 0.3, and 0.4) are used for each of the five pull-out speeds (10 m/s, 20 m/s, 30 m/s, 40 m/s, and 50 m/s). The curves show that pull-out force consists of approximately linear increasing portion and nonlinear decreasing portion with oscillations, as is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3. Slip-stick process causing oscillations at the pull-out force curve

Fig. 4. Displacement vs. time profile of two ends of pull-

out yarn

Fig. 5. Representative pull-out force vs. displacement curve for different pull-out speed: (a) 10 m/s, (b) 20 m/s, (c) 30 m/s, (d) 40 m/s, (e) 50 m/s

(a) Stress increases; consists of stage 1

(b) Stress decreases; consists of stage 2

Fig. 6. Stress distribution along pull-out yarn, during the pull-out process, at pull-out speed of 10 m/s and 0.3 friction coefficient (ms = millisecond)

(a) Friction along pulled yarn; consists of stage 1

(b) Friction along pulled yarn; consists of stage 2

Fig. 7. Friction force per unit length along pull-out yarn during the pull-out process (ms = millisecond)

Fig. 5a-e shows that increasing friction coefficient results in larger frictional shear force and larger pull-out force. As shown in Fig. 5a, the peak pull-out force increases from 2.43N to 25.68N when the friction coefficient increases from 0.2 to 0.4 for 10 m/s pull-out speed. Fig. 6 shows the distribution of stresses along the length of the pulled yarn at a pull-out speed of 10 m/s at a friction coefficient of 0.3. Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b show the stress distribution in stage 1 and stage 2, respectively, at various times during the pull-out process. In stage 1, the pull-out force increases and the yarn tension expands gradually from the pulled end to the free end. Once the yarn tension reaches the free end, sliding between the fabric and the pulled yarn begins. The stress increases in each time step and reaches a maximum at peak pull-out force. In stage 2, the yarn tension decreases when the free end of the pulled yarn passes a cross-yarn. The stress decreases in each time step. The stresses are plotted at several peak points of the oscillations in stage 2. Fig. 7

describes the distribution of friction force per unit length along the length of the pulled yarn at various times during the pull-out process. Fig. 7a shows that the friction force increases in stage 1 based on the movement of yarn coordinate and reaches the maximum at the peak pull-out force. The peak location in each curve is related to the uncrimping process of the pulled yarn. When the yarn movement is transferred to the free end of the yarn, the peak point of friction force in each curve occurs at the center of the fabric, where the friction is dominant due to the transverse preload and maximum contact force. The friction forces are plotted at several peak points of the oscillations in stage 2 at the same times as Fig. 6. Fig. 8 shows the yarn velocity along the pulled yarn length in stage 1. The yarn movement occurs with the yarn uncrimping process. The pull-out speed is transferred to the free end when the yarn is stretched, until it reaches the value of pull-out speed when the free end starts to slide. A large scatter at free end of the yarn is observed since the free end deforms freely without any constraint.

Effect of Friction Coefficient

To investigate the effect of friction coefficient, the peak pull-out force and pull-out energy are used for comparison. Fig. 9 shows the pull-out energy vs. yarn displacement at a pull-out speed of 10 m/s. The curve shows that the pull-out energy is significantly increased with increasing friction coefficient. Fig. 10 shows that the maximum pull-out force increases quadratically with friction coefficient at each pull-out speed. Increasing friction coefficient

Fig. 8. Pull-out speed along pull-out yarn coordinate at various times (10 m/s pull-out speed)

Fig. 9. Yarn pull-out energy at different friction coefficient

Fig. 10. Maximum pull-out force vs. friction coefficient at different pull-out speed

Fig. 11. Pull-out yarn uncrimping energy vs. friction coefficient at different pull-out speed

increases the frictional shear force and hence leads to an increase of pull-out force. The uncrimping energy also shows a quadratic increase with friction coefficient at each level of pull-out speed, as shown in Fig. 11. The increase in uncrimping energy can be linked to the increased pull-out force from higher frictional resistance, since energy is proportionally related to the product of pull-out force and yarn displacement.

Effect of Pull-out Speed

The effect of pull-out speed on the peak pull-out force and pull-out energy is also investigated. Fig. 12 shows the pull-out energy as a function of displacement at different pull-out speeds. The curves show that the pull-out energy increases significantly with pull-out speed. Fig. 13 shows that the maximum pull-out force increases approximately linear with pull-out speed at each friction coefficient. Increasing pull-out speed increases the cross-yarn tension which affects the contact force and leads to an increase in the pull-out force. The uncrimping energy shows a linear increase with pull-out speed in Fig. 14 at each level of friction coefficient. The increase in uncrimping energy is linked to the increased pull-out force caused by increased contact force from cross-yarns. Fig. 15 shows the stress distribution along the pulled yarn at the time where pull-out forces reach to the maximum at each pull-out speed. A higher pull-out speed increases the peak pull-out force which also increases the yarn stress along the pulled yarn. The flat portion in the curve corresponds to the out of fabric length of the pulled yarn for which there is no more frictional resistance from cross-yarns and the tensile force remains constant.

Fig. 12. Effect of pull-out speed on the energy displacement curve (friction coefficient of 0.3 is used)

Fig. 13. Maximum yarn pull-out force vs. pull-out speed at different friction coefficient

Fig. 14. Pull-out yarn uncrimping energy vs. pull-out speed at different friction coefficient

Conclusion

The numerical dynamic yarn pull-out test at fiber-level using explicit digital element method is conducted on Kevlar KM2. The pull-out behavior of a single yarn with constant pull-out speeds of 10 m/s, 20m/s, and 30m/s, 40 m/s, and 50 m/s at three levels of friction coefficients is presented in this paper. The results show that increasing pull-out speed and friction coefficient significantly increases the pull-out force. The energy needed to pull the yarn out also depends strongly on pull-out speed and friction coefficient. The yarn stress increases along the yarn length, starting from the free end, and smoothens

Fig. 15. Stress distribution along pulled yarn at peak pull-out force of each pull-out speed level

toward the pulled end where the yarn is pulled out of the fabric at each time step. The friction force increases along the yarn length, starting from the free end, reaches a maximum and decreases toward the pulled end where the yarn becomes straightened in stage 1. The peak point of the friction force moves towards the center of the fabric at the end of stage 1. In stage 2, the maximum friction force at each time step occurs at the center of the fabric, where the friction is dominant due to the transverse preload and maximum contact force. The yarn sliding transfers to the free end gradually along with yarn uncrimping process. More research is needed to investigate the relationship between fabric yarn pull-out properties and ballistic impact resistance. An attempt is also needed to validate the result of numerical simulation with experimental data.

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